

CARING FROM NURSE' PERCEPTIONS: A GROUNDED THEORY STUDY

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Abstract

Caring is the basic to the nursing role to associated patient satisfaction with care. The study were examined the caring behavior from nurse' perceptions. 5 nurse staffs from a public health center in Manado were deeply interviewed and then the data was analyzed thematically. The result identified six themes namely caring attitude towards patient health problems, responsible for solving patients' health problems, empathy attitude towards the client, respect for the patients' decision, friendly in caring for the patient, and take care without discriminating the patient. This study recommends that caring behavior caring must be reflected in every interaction of nurses and clients. Implementation of caring will improve the quality of nursing care and enhance patient satisfaction.

Keywords: *Caring, nurses, perception*

1. INTRODUCTION

Health professionals dedicate their careers to improving the lives of patients. In a hospital environment, nurses tend to have more interaction with patients. Patients in a state of vulnerability yearn for compassion and reassurance from those they intrinsically trust. One of the basic principles of the nursing process is that the care should be holistic, considering the patients, physical environment of hospital as well as the clients' families (1). Caring is the basic to the nursing role to associated patient satisfaction with care.

Watson (2008) states that human care is the heart of nursing. In the practice of nursing "caring" is aimed at health care that is holistic in increasing control, knowledge and promotion of health. The practice of caring integrates biophysical knowledge and human behavior to improve health (2). Effective caring will improve the health status and development of individuals and families. This study aims to get perspective of caring from nurse.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research is a qualitative design with a grounded theory approach. Participants were 5 nurses in hospital and 5 nurses in Puskesmas in Manado, Indonesia. Data collection was carried out through in-depth interviews with interview guidelines. This guide consists of 2 questions about caring behavior. Data were analyzed using Colaizzi thematic analysis.

3. RESULTS

The study results provide a theoretical conceptualization that describes what nurse perception about caring. This theoretical conceptualization builds on a core category: "A form of nursing care that gives holistic care to patients". In addition to these core categories, the six

related categories in theoretical conceptualization describe the strategy of how nurses apply caring behaviors to patients: (i) "caring attitude towards patient health problems", (ii) "responsible for solving patients' health problems", (iii) "empathy attitude towards the client", (iv) "respect for the patients' decision", (v) "friendly in caring for the patient", (vi) "take care without discriminating the patient". Figure 1.

3.1. Caring attitude towards patient health problems

"Caring is helping the needs of patients, prioritizing the interests of patients caring behaviors, caring for others caring for all the needs of patients holistically from the need of clothing, food, and spiritual". (*"Caring itu membantu kebutuhan pasien, mengutamakan kepentingan pasien sikap atau perilaku peduli, kepedulian terhadap orang lain.... merawat segala kebutuhan pasien secara holistic mulai dari kebutuhan berpakaian, makan, hingga kebutuhan secara spiritual".*)

Caring nurse is a caring behavior; take care of all the needs of patients holistically. This finding is supported by several theories stating nurses' caring attitude is manifested by nurses with a quick attitude to serve patients, care for the patient's condition and suffering, have a positive response in accepting, and behave caring to others. According to Watson (2007) the essence of caring is shown by the attitude of nurses who care about the needs and welfare of patients and their families. Attitudes of nurses who are concerned about meeting the needs of patients include ten carative factors of caring nurses (3).

3.2. Responsible to solve patients' health problems

".....when the nurse has finished shift and the patient arrives, the nurse still has to serve....the first is given services and then ask about patient insurance".

(*"...pasien sudah datang dari jauh walaupun sudah selesai jam shifts kerja kita tetap harus melayani..... masalah jaminan pasien ditanyakan setelah pasien diberikan pelayanan".*)

Research reveals that nurses are responsible for solving patients' health problems which are the core moral values of nurses in carrying out their roles. Leininger (1997) caring is the essence of nursing that is the core moral values of nursing based on human values and prioritizes the welfare of others, in this case the patient and his family (4). Caring behavior is the core moral values of nursing, where the core moral and ethical nursing is the responsibility in providing nursing services to patients, nurses have a response to what they do whether good or not morally good (5).

According to Potter & Perry (2006) nurses have the role of providing assistance for patients and families to set nursing goals. This role is a form of nurse's responsibility. The responsibility in carrying out the task will be seen from a professional nurse by presenting caring in all nursing service activities. Caring behavior is a form of nurse's responsibility for his role. The core sense of responsibility is the sensitivity of nurses to the health problems of patients and families, concerned with the situations and conditions in which patients are treated (6).

3.3. Empathy

"..... empathy to others.....respond to patient complaint".

(*"..... empati terhadap orang lain..... menanggapi keluhan pasien".*)

The results showed empathy is a form of caring attitude for nurses. The nurse applies a caring attitude by listening to the patient's feelings, sharing in feeling when the patient feels pain. Specific personal characteristics and personality traits include nurse emotions, attitudes, empathy, and organizational responses. Personal characteristics such as conscience, religion, beliefs, philosophy, commitment, response, and altruism contribute to nurses caring behavior (7). Nurses who have these characteristics will find it easier to apply caring and empathy in conducting nursing care to patients.

3.4. Respect for the patients' decision

".....respect the patients' decision". (*"... menghormati dan menghargai keputusan pasien"*.) The results of the thematic analysis show that nurses caring nurses can be done by respecting and respecting patients' decisions. The caring environment is offers development from potential existing, and at the same time let someone choose the best action for him at that time (Watson, 2004)(8). Respecting of patient decisions means that we provide moral support to patients who can motivate patients to recover. Patients will grow motivated if there is support for the treatment process. Leininger & Farland (2002) said that the process of assistance given by nurses to patients is intuitive or cognitive creative based on developing human values, respecting human dignity, instilling mutual trust and respecting humanity (9).

3.5. Take care of the patient friendly

".....we serve well.....we greet our patients.....speak politely".
(*"..... kita melayani dengan baik..... kita menyapa, memberikan salam kepada pasien..... bertutur kata juga harus baik"*.)

The results showed nurses behaved caring by being friendly to patients. A nurse who is friendly and patient in serving patients will provide comfort to patients who are hospitalized and need the help of nurses. Feeling comfortable will help patients get healing because psychologically patients will feel safe when served by friendly and patient nurses. A good nurse is friendly, sincere, full of patience, familiar with patients and focused on solving patient health problems.

Caring is grounded on a set of universal humanistic altruistic values. Humanistic values include kindness, empathy, concern, and love for self and others. Altruistic values arise from commitments to and satisfaction from receiving through giving. They bring meaning to one's life through one's belief and relationships with other people. Humanistic-altruistic feelings and acts provide the basis of human caring and promote the best professional care, and as such, constitute the first and most basic factor for science and ethic of caring (3)

Caring behavior will have implications for nursing practice so that caring nurses will speak kindly and politely, have attention, are full of interest in helping patients (10). Friendly is one component of the ten carative factors. Friendly attitude of nurses will make patients feel close and close in interpersonal relationships with nurses. This will make patients free to express their complaints, so nurses will get complete and accurate information.

3.6. No-discrimination to patient

"...take care without discriminating the patient". ("....perhatian tanpa membedakan pasien".)

The results of the thematic analysis also show that nurses caring nurses can be done by take care to patients without discrimination. Rooddeghan, ParsaYekta, & Nasarbadi (2017), state that equity in providing care is a major value in the nursing profession. Equitable care aims to provide the entire population with safe, efficient, reliable, and quality nursing services at all levels of health (11).

Watson (2008) said that creating an environment that supports healing for patients is included in the ten carative factors of caring nurses (2). ANA (2018) recommended that, nurses in all environments and at all levels must embrace the concepts of justice and caring, diversity and inclusiveness, and civility and mutual respect as guiding principles within the provision of health care. A nurse devotes herself to looking after and caring for clients without distinguishing them in any way. Every appropriate action and intervention carried out by a nurse will be very valuable for the lives of others. A nurse also carries a very important function and role in providing holistic nursing care to clients (12)

Figure 1. A Theory Conceptualization of Caring from Nurses' Perceptions

4. CONCLUSIONS

Caring is central to nursing practice because caring is a dynamic approach, where nurses work to further enhance their concern for clients. Based on the benefits of caring, caring must be reflected in every interaction of nurses and clients. This is accordance with the demands of society which is expecting quality nursing services. Implementation of caring will improve the quality of nursing care and enhance patient satisfaction.

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